

PERCEPTION OF E-WASTE AWARENESS, MANAGEMENT AND DISPOSAL OF SECONDARY LEVEL TEACHER TRAINEES

E.V.AVINEETHINI

Research scholar, Sri Sarada College of Education, Salem-16.

Dr.V.PRIYA

Research supervisor and Assistant professor of physical science, Sri Sarada College of Education, Salem-16.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to find out the perception of e-waste pollution and its relationship between the dimensions viz management and disposal of secondary level teacher trainees. Environmental issues are the major threats for many consequences happening now a day. E-waste become one the most important environmental issues in today's electronic world. In this study, normative survey method was adopted. The sample consists of 1774 B.Ed, teacher trainees from Tamilnadu, India. The findings obtained from the research shows that gender doesn't made any significant difference among the B.Ed, teacher trainees. There was a significant difference obtained from the trainee teachers who were studying environmental as a subject, being a member of eco- club and studying science as a stream of study. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that introducing environmental education as a major subject and encourages the trainees to get participated in awareness programmes related to environmental issue which enable them to understand the environmental issues.

Keywords: E-waste pollution, awareness, management, disposal, Secondary level teacher trainees.

INTRODUCTION

Now a day's development of science and technology has bring the world in to our hands, by swiping with the android phones individuals assess information and get all sort of things through online markets. Electronic industries are increased in numbers due to urbanizing and all human activities are controlled by the electronic devices. Numerous types of electronic devices are used by the people hence urges the high level of production of electronic equipments by the industries. When the e-product fails to functioning within its life time, few internal technical problems, nearing its life time and expiry of its life times or reached end life are known as e-waste. Sometimes we refuse to repair and reuse the e-waste. The source of e-waste refers to all types unused, expired and unfit for usages of electrical and electronic products considered as waste by the users like televisions, mobile phones, remote controllers, kitchen appliances, washing machines, dish washers, air conditioners, microwave ovens, batteries, wires, digital calculators, computers, laptops, light emitting lamps, water heater, mobile phone chargers, head sets, kids electronic toys with remote controllers, personal hygienic equipments, digital clocks, printers, scanners, medical equipments and industrial electronic machineries, etc. E-waste contains rich source and valuable substances and also harmful substances are presents in the e-wastes which cause harmful effects to the environment, human and ecological components. There are various harmful chemicals like Mercury, Lead, Barium, Chromium Cadmium, Arsenic, Beryllium and Nickel on the other hand some non hazardous chemical substances like gold, copper, aluminum, iron, silicon, zinc are presents in the e-wastes. The harmful chemicals affect and create various types of issues to the environment especially the human, the toxic chemicals creates health issues to the humans, animals and plants. The hazardous arise due to improper awareness, management, recycling of e-waste and improper disposal. Most of the products can be used again, donated within their community people which leads to less harmful to our environment.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

We are living in digital era; all the human activities are depended and controlled by the electronic devices. During pandemic period human beings mainly depending on electronic devices. These electronic devices become e-waste when its life time expires. Huge amount of e-waste generated every years which are harmful to our environment and living things. We are the first generation experiencing more environmental related issues compare to past generations. Awareness, management and

disposal were the primary source to overcome any sort of environmental issues. Most of the non-renewable resources were vanished by our generation; nothing was left out for our future generation. This is the crucial time for us to rectify our error by recycling, reusing our e-wastes for our betterment environment. Hence the present study deals with the e-waste pollution.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Pinar Ozdemir Deniz, et.al (2019) undertook a cross-sectional study on e-waste awareness in turkey. First year and fourth year engineering students from various departments were selected. Findings showed that gender doesn't have any significant difference in e-waste pollution and also the positive low level of correlation exists between awareness and e-waste regulation. Most of the students keep the e-waste in their home and they were not ready to donate with their friends and family members. While disposal of e-waste most of them burry in the landfill and no idea about the disposal of e-waste. Awareness about e-waste should be incorporated with the curriculum at the graduate level and also practical session introduced rather than the theory session to increase the knowledge and awareness about e-waste pollution.

Ayse Nesibe Koklukaya, et.al (2017) pointed out the importance of electromagnetic pollution and its effects. The researcher undertook a study on pre-service teacher trainees' awareness level of electromagnetic pollution. 76 pre-service teachers were selected through purposive sampling method from Ankara, Turkey. The result revealed that gender does not make any significant difference towards the awareness level of electromagnetic pollution and the female had scored a higher mean score than the male. The second interesting result was made based on an environmental course. The trainees who are taking environmental as a subject had significantly differed from those who had not taken environmental as a subject. There was no relationship between the awareness level of electromagnetic pollution and using an electromagnetic device. The investigator suggested to include electromagnetic pollution and other related concepts should be incorporated with the curriculum.

C.D. Licy, et.al (2013) probed awareness level of school student household and e-waste in Kerala. The secondary and higher secondary student has participated in this study. The secondary students had attended environmental awareness programmes showed a high level of awareness compared to the higher secondary students evident that awareness programmes had a significant effect. The type of family had no significant difference in solid waste. The students are willing to co-operate with the disposal of e-waste and other solid waste management. Awareness programmes were vital for sustainable development.

Sindhu Bala and Sukirti Goel (2012) conducted a study on e-waste management. 200 undergraduate students which include professional and non-professional streams in Noida city had selected for the study, the findings indicated that there was no awareness regarding the awareness level of the undergraduate students. The science students had more awareness level than the art students. The undergraduate students show a low level of e-waste management. Finally, the researcher suggested that regarding the e-waste very low level of awareness and management had seen in the graduates. Proper awareness and management skills were needed to educate individuals.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the differences in perception on e-waste pollution of B.Ed teacher trainees
- To compare the relationship between the dimensions of e-waste.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- There is no significance difference between the male and female B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution.
- There is no significance difference between the arts stream and science stream B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution.
- There is no significance difference between the eco-club member and non-member B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution.
- There is no significance difference between studying and studied environmental science as a subject B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution.
- There is no significance relationship between the dimensions of perception on e-waste pollution.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Research method:** For the present study normative survey method was chosen.
- **Sample:** The sample consists of 1774 secondary level teacher trainees who were studying two year B.Ed programme during the year 2017-2019. The trainees were selected from eighteen colleges from five districts namely Dharmapuri, Krishnagiri, Salem, Vellore and Thiruvannamalai in Tamilnadu, India.
- **Sampling technique:** Stratified random sampling technique was used for the present study.
- **Tool used:** E-waste pollution scale was developed by the researcher. It measures the awareness, management and disposal of pollution. Each dimension consists of seven questionnaires, totally twenty one items in the e-waste pollution questionnaire.
- **Reliability of the tool:** Cronbach's alpha method was used. The values were calculated as, 0.834, 0.832 and 0.834 for e-waste pollution awareness, e-waste pollution management and e-waste pollution disposal respectively.
- **Scoring procedure for e-waste pollution scale:** The tool e-waste pollution consists of 21 items. E-waste pollution item were based on Likert scale of summated rating answer in terms of five alternatives, in the case of E-waste pollution awareness, "Not at all aware, slightly aware, moderately aware, very aware, and extremely aware" weighing scores 1,2,3,4, and 5 respectively. All the items the tool was positive. E-waste management and disposal dimension items followed by five alternatives ranging from never (1), rarely (2), sometimes (3), often (4) and always (5) respectively. The E-waste disposal consist of (e-waste pollution) seven items, in which all the items are positive except the two items (16, and 20) are negative items and which are reversely scored

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The analysis of data for the present study was done on the basis of formulated hypothesis of the study. The resulting data were analyzed based on the hypothesis by using appropriate statistical techniques.

Hypothesis-1: There is no significance difference between the male and female B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution.

DIMENSIONS	GENDER	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	't' VALUE	S/NS LEVEL(0.5)
EWPA	Male	473	22.78	4.31	1.03	NS
	Female	1301	23.02	4.55		
EWPM	Male	473	21.37	5.60	0.86	NS
	Female	1301	21.63	5.51		
EWPD	Male	473	15.77	5.12	1.80	NS
	Female	1301	16.27	5.10		
EWP	Male	473	59.93	12.70	1.48	NS
	Female	1301	60.92	11.82		

Table-1: showing the mean difference of male and female B.Ed, teacher trainees on E-waste pollution

From the above Table-1, it is evident that the calculated value for e-waste pollution 1.48 is lesser than the critical value 1.96 which is not significant at 0.05 levels. In dimensions wise EWPA, EWPM and EWPD calculated 't' values were 1.03, 0.86 and 1.08 respectively. It indicates that the mean score of male and female do not differ significantly with respect to e-waste pollution and its dimensions. Thus the null hypothesis that there is no significance difference between the male and female B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution is accepted. Further the mean score of EWP of female 60.92 which is higher than the mean score of male 59.93 with corresponding standard deviation 11.82 and 12.70 respectively. It may therefore, said that female were found to have slightly higher in e-waste pollution awareness, management and disposal as compared to their male counterpart. Thus it is concluded that "There is no significance difference between the male and female B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution" is accepted at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis-2: There is no significance difference between the arts stream and science stream B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution

DIMENSIONS	STREAM OF THE STUDY	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	't' VALUE	S/NS LEVEL(0.5)
EWPA	Arts	529	21.00	4.08	12.93	S(0.5)
	Science	1245	23.85	4.33		
EWPM	Arts	529	19.85	5.21	8.86	S(0.5)
	Science	1245	22.30	5.52		
EWPD	Arts	529	14.11	4.25	12.23	S(0.5)
	Science	1245	17.00	5.21		
EWP	Arts	529	54.95	10.76	14.13	S(0.5)
	Science	1245	63.08	11.78		

Table-2: showing the mean difference of Arts and Science stream B.Ed, teacher trainees on E-waste pollution

From the above Table-2, it is evident that the calculated value for e-waste pollution 14.13 is greater than the critical value 1.96 which is significant at 0.05 levels. In dimensions wise EWPA, EWPM and EWPD calculated' values were 12.93, 8.86 and 12.23 respectively. It indicates that the mean score of Arts and Science as a stream of study do differ significantly with respect to e-waste pollution and its dimensions. Thus the null hypothesis that there is no significance difference between the Arts and Science as a stream of study B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution is rejected. Further the mean score of EWP of science as a stream of study 63.08 which is higher than the mean score of arts 54.95 with corresponding standard deviation 11.78 and 10.76 respectively. It may therefore, said that science as a stream of study were found to have higher in e-waste pollution awareness, management and disposal as compared to their art as a stream of the study counterpart. Thus it is concluded that "There is no significance difference between the Arts and Science as a stream of study B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution" is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis-3: There is no significance difference between the eco-club member and non-member B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution

DIMENSIONS	ECO-CLUB	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	't' VALUE	S/NS LEVEL(0.5)
EWPA	Member	784	24.58	4.42	14.35	S(0.5)
	Non-member	990	21.67	4.05		
EWPM	Member	784	22.71	5.31	7.93	S(0.5)
	Non-member	990	20.65	5.54		
EWPD	Member	784	17.42	5.42.	9.45	S(0.5)
	Non-member	990	15.12	4.62		
EWP	Member	784	64.71	11.71	13.14	S(0.5)
	Non-member	990	57.45	11.37		

Table-3: showing the mean difference of eco-club member and non-member B.Ed, teacher trainees on E-waste pollution

From the above Table-3, it is evident that the calculated value for e-waste pollution 13.14 is greater than the critical value 1.96 which is significant at 0.05 levels. In dimensions wise EWPA, EWPM and EWPD calculated' values were 14.35, 7.93 and 9.45 respectively. It indicates that the mean score of eco-club member and non-member do differ significantly with respect to e-waste pollution and its dimensions. Thus the null hypothesis that there is no significance difference between the eco-club member and non-member B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution is rejected. Further the mean score of EWP of eco-club member 64.71 which is higher than the mean score of non-member 57.45 with corresponding standard deviation 11.71 and 11.37 respectively. It may therefore, said that eco-club member were found to have higher in e-waste pollution awareness, management and disposal as compared to their non-member counterpart. Thus it is concluded that "There is no significance difference between the eco-club member and non-member B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution" is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis-4: There is no significance difference between studying environmental science as a subject and studied B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution

DIMENSIONS	YEAR OF STUDY	N	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	't' VALUE	S/NS LEVEL(0.5)
EWPA	Studying	940	23.80	4.69	8.73	S(0.5)
	Studied	834	22.01	3.94		
EWPM	Studying	940	22.18	5.27	4.99	S(0.5)
	Studied	834	20.86	5.75		
EWPD	Studying	940	16.58	5.23	3.94	S(0.5)
	Studied	834	15.63	4.93		
EWP	Studying	940	62.57	12.04	7.17	S(0.5)
	Studied	834	58.51	11.74		

Table-4: showing the mean difference of studying environmental science as a subject and studied B.Ed, teacher trainees on E-waste pollution

From the above Table-4, it is evident that the calculated value for e-waste pollution 7.17 is greater than the critical value 1.96 which is significant at 0.05 levels. In dimensions wise EWPA, EWPM and EWPD calculated 't' values were 8.73, 4.99 and 3.94 respectively. It indicates that the mean score of studying environmental science as a subject and studied environmental science as a subject do differ significantly with respect to e-waste pollution and its dimensions. Thus the null hypothesis that there is no significance difference between the studying environmental science as a subject and studied environmental science as a subject B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution is rejected. Further the mean score of EWP of studying environmental as a subject 62.57 which is higher than the mean score of studied 58.51 with corresponding standard deviation 12.04 and 11.74 respectively. It may therefore, said that science as a stream of study were found to have higher in e-waste pollution awareness, management and disposal as compared to their studied environmental as a subject counterpart. Thus it is concluded that "There is no significance difference between the studying environmental science as a subject and studied B.Ed teacher trainees towards the perception on e-waste pollution" is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis-5: There is no significance relationship between the dimensions of perception on e-waste pollution.

E-WASTE POLLUTION	EWPA	EWPM	EWPD
EWPA	1	.449	.458
EWPM		1	.461
EWPD			1

Table-5: showing the Relationship between the dimensions of E-waste pollution of B.Ed, teacher trainees

The above Table-5 shows the calculated 'r' values of e-waste pollution between the dimensions. Significant relationship was found in all cases. Hence the formulated null hypothesis is rejected in all the cases. There is a moderate positive significant relationship exists between the dimensions of EWPA and EWPM, EWPA and EWPD and EWPM and EWPD.

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the above mentioned hypotheses indicate the perception of e-waste pollutions and its dimensions based on demographic variables. Gender does not make any significance which confirms the result of Deniz P.O. et.al (2019) and Ayse Nesibe Koklukaya, et.al. (2017) also found no significance based on gender. In present study female had higher mean score which confirms with the result of Ayse Nesibe Koklukaya, et.al. (2017). Furthermore the study reveals science trainees had significant difference with arts which confirms the result of Sindhu Bala and Sukirti Goel (2012) also found science students differ from art students. the present study reveals that studying environmental as a subject differ significantly with their counterparts which confirms the result of Ayse Nesibe Koklukaya, et.al. (2017) who also found that environmental subject taking students differ significantly compare to the non taking environmental paper. From the study it is evident that there is moderate positive relationship exist between the dimensions of e-waste pollutions which is contrast with the findings of Deniz P.O. et.al (2019) who found low positive relationship between the awareness level of e-waste pollution.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that environmental education subject should be incorporated in all levels of education starting from primary level to university level. Awareness programmes and seminars regarding environmental issues should be conducted in every academic year. By increasing the number of environmental course will definitely raise the awareness level and also environmental literacy.

CONCLUSION

The present study aimed to find out the perception of e-waste pollution awareness, management and disposal. The level of e-waste pollution awareness, management and disposal and its consequences were influenced by multiple factors of gender, stream of the study, member of eco club and studying environmental course as a subject. There is a moderate positive significant relationship exists between the dimensions of e-waste pollution. As the result obtained by the analysis of data it has been found that, gender does not made any significant difference in e-waste pollution and its dimensions. The findings of the present study reveals that the B.Ed, teacher trainees who were studying environmental as a subject, being a member of eco-club and science as a stream of study has a significant difference in e-waste pollution awareness, management and disposal compared with their counterparts. The reason may be they gaining theoretical as well as practical knowledge on e-waste pollution and its consequences. The knowledge with relation to the basic environmental related concepts help the trainees to implement in to practices. From the result it is evident that importance of environmental education and also awareness programmes related to current environmental issues. The B.Ed teacher trainees are going to impart the environmental knowledge, basic concepts to their next generation to raise environmentally responsible citizen.

LIST OF ACRONYM

EWP	-	Electronic Waste Pollution
EWPA	-	Electronic Waste Pollution Awareness
EWPM	-	Electronic Waste Pollution Management
EWPD	-	Electronic Waste Pollution Disposal
E-waste	-	Electronic Waste
B.Ed	-	Bachelor of Education

REFERENCES

- [1] Awasthi, A. K., Zeng, X., & Li, J. (2016). Environmental pollution of electronic waste recycling in India: a critical review. *Environmental pollution*, 211, 259-270.
- [2] Bala, S., & Goel, S. (2012). A study of e-waste management in relation to awareness of college students. *Int J Educ Psychol Res*, 2, 31-35.
- [3] Deniz, P. Ö., Aydın, Ç. Y., & Kiraz, E. D. E. (2019). Electronic waste awareness among students of engineering department. *Cukurova Medical Journal*, 44(1), 101-109.
- [4] Gümrükçüoğlu, N., Sarimehmet, D., & Hintistan, S. (2017). Environmental Awareness and Knowledge Level of Higher Education Students. Online Submission.
- [5] Jekria, N., & Daud, S. (2016). Environmental concern and recycling behaviour. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35, 667-673.
- [6] Licy, C. D., Vivek, R., Saritha, K., Anies, T. K., & Josphina, C. T. (2013). Awareness, attitude and practice of school students towards household waste management. *Journal of Environment*, 2(6), 147-150.
- [7] Koklukaya, A. N., Yildirim, E. G., & Selvi, M. (2017). The Relationship between Pre-service Teachers' Awareness Levels of Electromagnetic Pollution and other Environmental Problems. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 16(67).
- [8] Konur, K. B., & Akyol, N. (2017). Preschool Students' Perceptions on Environmental Problems. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*.
- [9] Mary, J. S., & Meenambal, T. (2016). Inventorisation of e-waste and developing a policy–bulk consumer perspective. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 35, 643-655.
- [10] Metin, M. (2010, December). A study on developing a general attitude scale about environmental issues for students in different grade levels. In *Asia-Pacific Forum on Science Learning and Teaching* (Vol. 11, No. 2, pp. 1-19). The Education University of Hong Kong, Department of Science and Environmental Studies.
- [11] Miner, K. J., Rampedi, I. T., Ifegbesan, A. P., & Machete, F. (2020). Survey on Household Awareness and Willingness to Participate in E-Waste Management in Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria. *Sustainability*, 12(3), 1047.
- [12] Mureithi, M., & Waema, T. (2008). *E-waste Management in Kenya*. Nairobi: Kenya ICT Action Network (KICTANet).
- [13] Patowary, P., & Baishya, P. (2020). Environmental Awareness among Higher Secondary School Students—A Study. *Our Heritage*, 68(30), 13053-13058.
- [14] Saito, R., Kimura, R., & Tsuda, A. (2014). A study of awareness and behavior of students about environmental issues in Makassar City. *Journal of the Tsuruma Health Science Society Kanazawa University*, 38, 75-83.